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Education as a Tool to Govern British India

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ABSTRACT :

The purpose of this study is to explore the steps of British government in educating the Indian masses. The study is based on secondary source of data. The British's come India for the purpose of trade in the form of East India Company. As soon as time passes they annexed a number of states. To govern on these states they need educate people. To take all the people from their homeland was most costly. This urges the British Government to start education in India. The purpose was to prepare a class of people which acts as a bridge between the British's and Indian masses.

KEY WORDS:

Education, Woods Despatch, Macaulay's Minute, Committee, vernacular language, Government.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To explore the Education policies of British Government in India.
2. To explore the role of education in governing British India.

INTRODUCTION :

The British Empire in India lasted nearly 200 years. The English East India Company started trading activities in India in the early seventeenth century. In 1613, they received consent to build their factory Surat. The East India Company's victories in the battle of Plassey in 1757 and the battle of Buxar in 1764 gave them political control over the eastern states of Bengal and Bihar, and laid the foundations of the British Empire in India. Over the next hundred years, several areas were annexed to the British Empire. Many coastal regions of southern India were annexed by 1800, parts of northern India, Western India and Central India became part of the British Empire before 1820. Assam was conquered in the 1820's and Punjab in 1849. Among the last areas to be annexed in the 1850's were the northern native states of Oudh and the central Indian areas of Nagpur and Berar. In 1858, the administration of India was taken over by the British Crown from the East India Company and there were no further annexations.

The preliminary policies introduced by the directions of the East India Company promoted elitist English Education geared towards a small minority of the population- the higher castes and classes. An important objective of these policies was to "form a class of people who may be interpreters between us (the British) and the millions whom we govern". The hope was that this learned class would then enrich the

vernacular languages and educate the masses, while providing a steady labour supply to the colonial administration offices. Though later policies shifted the focal point to primary education, they met with incomplete success because primary education received less than 40% of public education expenditures. Moreover, in the 1880's primary schooling was decentralized to local boards where local factors became critical to the provision of schools. The number of public primary schools was lower in districts with higher levels of caste and religious diversity because traditional elites preferred developing secondary schools and perhaps due to lower demand for education among disadvantage groups like the lower castes and indigenous tribes.

BRITISH EDUCATION POLICIES

The East India Company was not able to afford the expenses of the high salaries of English officers. So the Company required local Indian employees, who were able to read, write and speak English. It was also hoped that education would provide a positive link between rulers and the ruled and lead to the permanence and stability of the British Raj. In the 18th century, Christian missionaries spread religious education pertaining Christianity in India. But the East India Company felt that it would encourage adversely religious sentiments among the Indian masses that could affect the business policy and the diplomatic role of the East India Company. Therefore, they did not support the missionaries for the promulgation of the religious education to the common people in India during the period from 1793 to 1812.

In 1813, the charter of the East India Company was renewed. Christian Religious institutions pressurized the British Parliament so that the Company charter contained a clause setting aside a lakh of rupees for education. The British Parliament insisted, in spite of opposition from the Directors of the Company on inserting a clause in the Charter, giving missionaries full freedom to settle and work in India. Soon afterwards, there was a great arrival of missionaries into India. These missionaries frequently opened schools, hospitals and orphanages. In March 1835, William Bentinck applied Modern Western Studies system in English language on the suggestion of his legal advisor Thomas Macaulay said that "we must at present do our best to form a class who may be interpreters between us and the millions whom we govern, a class of persons Indian in blood and colour, but English in tastes, in opinions, in morals and in intellect".

In 1844, Lord Harding's administration announced that all those educated in English would be preferred in office appointments. Given the new importance placed upon English training, English education began to flourish in India through both government and private schools. Lord Dalhousie also offered open support of government for educating girls.

During the time 1813-1853 CE, the colonial entity opened a few English schools and colleges instead of a large number of elementary schools, this led to the neglect of the education of the masses. This policy of colonial ruler was called Downwards Filtration Theory, which meant coming down of education or knowledge from the top to the bottom, i. e, from the higher class people to the lower classes or the general people. This policy was well supported by the contemporary higher officials such as Lord Macaulay. Filtration theory fulfilled the aim of Lord Macaulay and the directors of the company.

The British Educational policy continued on the basis of recommendations of Macaulay till changes were made under Dalhousie, although it was officially discarded in 1854 and hence began the next phase of colonial education in India. The British Empire had grown to full shape when Dalhousie came to India. Lord Dalhousie realized the need of mass education and desired to "establish a complete class of vernacular schools to expand throughout the whole of India, with a view to convey instructions to the masses of the people". When the time of renewal of charter came in 1853, the directors of the Company decided to lay

down a clear-cut policy for education in India and made a comprehensive survey of the entire field of education. As such a Selection Committee of the British Parliament was set up in order to institute an inquiry into the masses for their reforms. The Committee studied the issue thoroughly and reported that the question of Indian education should not be ignored and its development would not in any case be harmful to the British Empire. The suggestions of the Committee were positively considered by the board of Directors. As Sir Charles Wood was the president of the Board of control, so the declaration was called as “Wood’s Educational Despatch” though it was written by the famous thinker John Stuart mill.

Educational Despatch deals with the various aspects of educational importance and holds a unique place in the history of Indian education. Therefore, it is often described as the ‘Magna carta’ of modern education in India. For the first time, it clearly accepted the liability of the British Government for education in India. It officially discarded the ‘filtration theory’ and laid stress on mass education, female education and improvement of vernacular, favored secularism in education and teachers training.

In 1882, the Government of India constituted a Commission with the objective “to enquire into the manner in which effect had been given to the principles of the Despatch of 1854 and to suggest such measures as it may desirable in order to the further carrying out of the policy therein laid down”. The Commission was constituted by Lord Ripon under Sir W. W. Hunter, and therefore, it is also known as Hunter Commission. The Commission adopted the policy of Laissez faire and advocated the gradual withdrawal of the state from the direct support and management of institutions of higher education.

Hunter Commission recommended that local bodies should be entrusted with the management of primary schools. The Commission advised for increasing the number of high schools and colleges and emphasized that they should not only be maintained by government but some of them should also be run by private bodies. After the recommendations of Hunter Commission, Punjab University was formally constituted under the act of 1882 and Allahabad University under the Act of 1887. The number of colleges was also increased.

Lord Curzon appointed a University Commission under chairmanship of Thomas Raleigh (law member of the Viceroy’s executive Council) on 27th January, 1902. The purpose of the committee was to enquire into the conditions and prospects of the universities. The committee’s main finding was, ‘no change had been seen in university education because they failed to follow the guidelines of London University’.

The education progress received another impetus with the initiation by G. K. Gokhale with the introduction of a bill to make elementary education free, compulsory for children aged between 6 to 10 years. Gokhale’s efforts had far-reaching consequences in the subsequent period. His efforts were responsible for the creation of a separate education department in 1910 and the strengthening of the movement in favour of mass education.

The Calcutta University Commission was appointed by Viceroy Lord Chelmsford, the government of India in 1917, under the chairmanship of M. E. S. Sadler, to study its working. The Commission submitted a capacious report in 1919, practically dealing with every problem of Secondary and University Education, which was a great turning point, since its recommendations were adopted by several other universities.

The Central Advisory Board of Education (CABE) was established in 1921 to bring consensus on policy matters among provincial government, but it was not operational till 1935. During this period, education system came under the Indian control officially, as it became a provisional subject administered by provincial legislature under the provisions of the government of India Act of 1919. The Indian

government appointed Indian Statutory Commission on November 8, 1927, which was normally referred as Simon Commission. This Commission was made to enquire into the working of the administration under the government of India Act, 1919.

The government certified Simon Commission to appoint a Committee to help in preparing a report on education known as Hartong Committee to help in preparing a report on education known as Hartong Committee, under the leadership of sir Philip Hartong to enquire into the conditions of education in India. In 1929, Hartong Committee submitted its report and recommended the policy of consolidation, improvement of primary education. The Committee also recommended diversion of more boys to industrial and commercial careers at the end of the middle stage, preliminary to special instruction in technical and industrial schools and a selective system of admission to universities.

In 1935-36, the Central Advisory board of Education was revived and it recommended the appointment of a committee to advise the government "on certain problems of educational reorganization and particularly on problems of Vocational education". One of the basic reasons for instructing this enquiry was "the fact a large number of University graduates were not securing employment of kind for which their education qualified them". So the government of India invited two British experts, A. Abbott and S. H. Wood for preparing a plan on vocational education in the country. The committee strongly believed the problem of unemployment in India could be solved only through industrial development of the country. In June 1937, Abbott and Wood submitted their report in two parts viz., Technical and General, which was based on the experience of their visits to UP, Delhi and the Punjab and known as the Abbott-Wood report. On the technical parts, the report suggested a complete hierarchy of vocational institutions parallel general education. On the general part, the report suggested about the medium of education, which was similar to the earlier committee reports.

In 1937, the congress Ministry assumed accountability of administration in seven major provinces of India and concentrated their attention on educational reforms.

MEDICAL EDUCATION :

In 1869, the medical departments in the three presidencies were amalgamated into the Indian Medical Service. A competitive examination was conducted in London to recruit people into Indian Medical Service. The European officers of the Indian Medical Service headed the military and civil medical operations in the three presidencies. However, they needed trained assistants and supporting staff such as apothecaries, compounders and dressers in their work. Appointing European doctors had large financial implications. This prompted the British government to look towards establishing a system of medical education in India to recruit local staff.

In 1822, the Native Medical Institute was established in Calcutta to provide medical training to Indians. Around 20 young Indian students were instructed in the vernacular medium. European texts in anatomy, medicine and surgery were translated into the local language for the benefit of students. In 1826, classes on Unani medicine were held at the Calcutta Madrasa, while the Sanskrit college conducted classes in Ayurvedic medicine. Successive native graduates were absorbed into government jobs.

Calcutta Medical College was established in 1835 and it ushered in a new beginning to medical education in India. Youths between 14 and 20 years of age were trained in the principles and practices of medical science using methods of the west. Around 49 students were selected, some through a preliminary examination. They were to be trained for a period not less than 4 years and not more than 6 years, after which they had to appear in a final examination. Successful candidates were given certificates allowing them

to practice surgery and medicine. They were called “native doctors” and allowed to enter public service with an initial pay of Rs. 30 a month.

In March 1838, a generous grant by Philanthropist Sir Jamset jee jee jebhoy made way for building a new general hospital. The East India Company approved the proposal to setup a medical college on July 18, 1838. However, Sir Grant succumbed to illness 9 days before this news arrived. The new medical college was named after Grant as a tribute to him. The foundation stone of the Grant Medical College was laid in Bombay in March 1843 with an aim to “impart the benefits of medical instructions to the natives of Western India through a systematic system”. The general hospital which was opened in 1845 is now known as the Sir JJ Hospital.

The bright spots for medicine during colonial times were the initiation of public health measures, vaccination and the elevation of tropical disease to a special area of study. The state took responsibility for sanitation to a special are of study. The state took the responsibility for sanitation and hygiene. Collection of vital statistics was initiated. A number of epidemiological and research studies were conducted on cholera, plague, malaria, tuberculosis and leprosy.

CONCLUSION :

Education is main tool to train people in every field of life. The British Government uses this tool to rule on Indian people. They prepare a class of people who work as a bridge between Britishers and Indians. They have no intention to literate people of India but they need a number of educated people in every office which bound them to literate people of India. For this purpose they revise their education policies from time to time to give quality education to Indians. By revising the education policies they try to literate more and more Indians. By this they ruled India nearly 200 years.

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